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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION OF BMI WITH THE LIPID PROFILE AND
SERUM LEPTIN**Faizan Maqsood, Zulquernain Zahid, Aniq Liaquat
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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the possible relationship between serum leptin and lipid profile with obesity.

Place and duration of study: In the Medicine Unit of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for one-year duration from April 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: Patient consent was taken prior to their participation in this study. The subjects were divided into two categories; obese (BMI > 30) and non-obese (BMI < 25). The body weight of each individual dressed in light clothing was measured using accurately calibrated weight. The height of each individual was measured using a vertical measuring rod; waist and hips were also measured to calculate the waist to hip ratio. Blood samples were taken early in the morning, 12 hours after a meal. About 10 ml of venous blood was taken from the subjects. Serum samples were stored at 2-5 °C for no more than 24 hours before measurements of plasma lipid and leptin profile. An ELISA kit with human leptin (ENZO-ALX-850-044-K101) (which was designed by sandwich enzyme assay for quantitative measurement of human leptin) was used. Triacylglycerol concentration was measured by GPO PAP, for this purpose Triglyceride LABKIT was used. Cholesterol concentration was measured by CHOD / PAP method, for this purpose Cholesterol LABKIT was used.

Results: The average age of patients was 45.35 ± 5.96 years and was at least 32-58 years old. In total, 91 people were selected. 43 (47.3%) were men and the remaining 48 (52.7%) were women. The results show a positive significant correlation in BMI and serum leptin, $r = 0.316$ (0.002), a significant correlation in BMI and total cholesterol, $r = 0.095$ (0.000), a positive significant correlation in BMI and HDL cholesterol, $r = 0.008$ (0.000), no significant correlation in BMI and LDL cholesterol, $r = -0.001$ (0.747), no significant correlation in the ratio of BMI and LDL cholesterol to HDL cholesterol, $r = -0.041$ (0.270).

Conclusion: According to the results of this study, it can be concluded that there is a certain relationship between lipid profile and serum leptin and body mass index. Further research is needed to investigate the interaction of the peptide with the lipid profile and vice versa.

Key words: obesity, leptin, lipid profile, body mass index (BMI)

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INTRODUCTION:

Leptin plays an important role in regulating body weight, serving the brain as a signal of satiety of fat, affecting food intake and energy consumption in a negative feedback loop. Leptin mRNA and leptin secretion in adipocytes have been shown to be modulated by thyroid hormones¹⁻². Leptin has a number of regulatory functions; most of them are little known. Plasma leptin is strongly associated with cardiovascular risk factors such as obesity, insulin resistance, hypertension, dyslipidemia, hyperuricemia, and inflammatory markers³⁻⁴. Obesity is associated with at least a 3-fold increased risk of fatal and non-fatal myocardial infarction. The American Heart Association has reclassified obesity as an important and modifiable risk factor for coronary artery disease⁵⁻⁶. The higher incidence of ischemic heart disease in obesity is due to many factors. An important factor contributing to this severe incidence is changes in plasma lipid and lipoprotein levels⁷⁻⁸. Dyslipidemia in obesity usually occurs with small dense LDL particles, which are high density triacylglycerol, low density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDLc) and normal low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDLc). All this literature shows that there may be a reasonable relationship between plasma lipid profile and leptin⁹. Leptin is thought to provide feedback on body fat storage into the central nervous system. So; Leptin is thought to be involved in the regulation of appetite, food intake and lipid metabolism. Schoolchildren with higher plasma leptin levels have been reported to have higher triglycerides, LDL-c and Apo protein A than with relatively lower leptin levels¹⁰. In contrast, the relationship between leptin levels and lipid profile and lipoprotein levels was not statistically significant in adult patients with hyperlipidemia.

METHOD

In this study, 100 patients (50 obese and 50 non-obese) were selected from the Medicine Unit of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for one-year duration from April 2019 to March 2020. The local audit committee received ethical approval, and all participants have given approval. For the purposes of this study, entities were divided into two categories; Patients with obesity, BMI > 30 and patients without obesity, BMI < 25. Patients suffering from diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases or malignancies, hepatitis B or other infectious diseases are not included.

Analytical method: The nutritional status of all subjects was assessed by anthropometric measurements. The body weight of each individual dressed in light clothing was measured using a carefully calibrated weight. The height of each individual was measured with a vertical meter; The waist / hip circumference was also measured to calculate the waist to hip ratio. BMI was calculated by dividing the mass in kg by the height of the square (in m²). Blood samples were taken early in

the morning, 12 hours after the test. About 10 ml of venous blood will be taken from the patients. Serum samples were stored at 2-5 ° C for no more than 24 hours before determining the serum leptin and lipid profile (LDL, HDL, VLDL and LDL: HDL ratio).

Laboratory techniques:

1. Leptin measurement by ELISA: A human leptin ELISA kit (ENZO-ALX-850-044-KI01) (designed by sandwich enzyme assay for quantitative measurement of human leptin) was used.

2. Lipid profile Triacylglycerol concentration: Triacylglycerol concentration was measured by GPO-PAP, for this purpose LABKIT triglyceride was used. After measuring the absorbance of the standard and sample relative to the raw material at an altitude of 546 m within 60 minutes, the triglyceride concentration was determined using the following formula: triglyceride concentration (mg / dl) = standard sample / standard concentration X (mg / dl)

Cholesterol level:

Cholesterol concentration was measured by CHOD / PAP method, for this purpose Cholesterol LABKIT was used. After measuring the absorbance of the standard and sample relative to the raw material over 546 m over 60 minutes, cholesterol concentration was determined by entering the following formula: cholesterol concentration (mg / dl) = sample / standard concentration X standard (mg / dl)

HDL cholesterol concentration:

The method of phosphotungstic acid precipitation for HDL-cholesterol concentration was measured using HDL-Cholesterol LABKIT (ref. 30188). After measuring the absorbance of the standard and sample relative to the raw material over 546 m within 30 minutes, HDL cholesterol concentration was determined by adding the value to the formula: HDL cholesterol concentration (mg / dl) = factor A X

LDL cholesterol:

LDL cholesterol was measured by the Friedwald method. For measuring LDL cholesterol; Triglyceride, cholesterol and HDL levels were measured, and then their values were entered into the following formula: LDL cholesterol was measured (Friedwald et al., 1972): LDL cholesterol (mg / dl) = total cholesterol (mg / dl) - triglycerides / 5 (mg / dl) - HDL-cholesterol (mg / dl)

VLDL Cholesterol:

VLDL was measured by dividing triglycerides by 5: VLDL cholesterol (mg / dl): triglyceride concentration (mg / dl).

Statistical analysis: results are presented as mean +/- standard deviation. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 18 (SPSS, Evanston, IL, USA) for Windows. Undivided biochemical parameters were analyzed after normal logarithmic conversion. To compare the results of different groups, an unpaired student's t-test and one-way analysis of variance

(ANOVA) were used. Simple and partial correlation coefficients between variables were determined and multiple regression analysis was performed to determine the relationship between the respective

variables. Data are expressed as mean (SD) or median (range); Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Statistical analysis of lipid profile

	serum leptin (ng/ml)	TG (mg/dl)	T-Chol (mg/dl)	HDL-C (mg/dl)	LDL-C (mg/dl)	LDL-C/HDL-C ratio
BMI (Wt in Kg/ ht in m2)						
Correlation	.316(**)	.703(**)	.691(**)	.531(**)	.034	-.117
p-value	.002	.000	.000	.000	.747	.270
serum leptin (ng/ml)						
Correlation		.266(*)	.195	.108	-.001	-.041
p-value		.011	.064	.310	.993	.700
TG (mg/dl)						
Correlation			.619(**)	.631(**)	.098	-.061
p-value			.000	.000	.353	.568
T-Chol (mg/dl)						
Correlation				.531(**)	-.080	-.207(*)
p-value				.000	.453	.049
HDL-C (mg/dl)						
Correlation					-.068	-.301(**)
p-value					.524	.004
LDL-C (mg/dl)						
Correlation						.965(**)
p-value						.000

Table 2: Lipid profile in obese and non-obese patients

	Obesity	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
waist/hip ratio	Obese	1.076	0.059	0
	Non-obese	0.88	0.053	
serum leptin (ng/ml)	Obese	6.36	7.38	0.004
	Non-obese	3.13	0.617	
TAG (mg/dl)	Obese	193.04	23.225	0
	Non-obese	140.65	15.127	
T-Cholesterol (mg/dl)	Obese	216.08	31.249	0
	Non-obese	160.72	20.76	
HDLc (mg/dl)	Obese	66.45	16.099	0
	Non-obese	46.72	8.46	
LDLc (mg/dl)	Obese	151.35	27.18	0.893
	Non-obese	154.37	152.3	
LDLc:HDLc ratio	Obese	2.39	0.64	0.076
	Non-obese	3.54	4.3	
	Non-obese	1.97	0.264	

DISCUSSION:

Although much has been learned about the leptin hormone, its physiology, but its exact role in the endocrine system has not yet been identified¹¹⁻¹². One of the challenges inherent in these studies is that leptin physiology looks completely different in humans and rodents¹³⁻¹⁴. The circadian rhythm differs not only in plasma levels, but also in its regulation and relationship to other physiological parameters. The purpose of this study is to demonstrate the relationship between serum leptin and obesity with serum lipids. Current research shows that there is a significant positive correlation between BMI and total cholesterol, HDLc and GAD. However, no relationship was found between the ratio of LDLc and HDLc to LDLc¹⁵. The relationship between serum leptin and serum lipids is inconsistent, and in a Hallikainen study, high serum leptin was associated with high cholesterol synthesis and low cholesterol absorption, but with serum lipids. Leptin is associated with atherosclerosis and has been shown to disrupt lipoprotein profiles.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, significantly higher serum leptin was observed in obese patients. Because the sample size is small in this study, a comprehensive study should be conducted to fully understand the relationship between BMI and lipid profile and leptin levels. HDL, LDL and GAD levels affect a variety of factors and it cannot be concluded that the lipid profile determines the obesity of the individual. A detailed study should be designed and performed to take into account all factors associated with the lipid profile and the possible relationship between the lipid profile and obesity.

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